

Supplemental Materials

Figure S1. FGFR4 expression in the intestine of mice fed standard chow with or without proglumide in the drinking water. (A) Western blot of FGFR4 protein expression in Control mice on the left and in mice treated with proglumide on the right. (B) Densitometry analysis of western blot shows increased FGFR4 protein expression in the intestines of proglumide treated mice is 3-fold higher than controls (P=0.06).